

Abnormal Claisen Rearrangement of 3-Prenyloxyxanthone and 3-Prenyloxy-4-methylxanthone

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Claisen rearrangement of 3-prenyloxyxanthone (1), when refluxed with dimethylaniline gave 4-(1,2-dimethylpropenyl)-3-hydroxyxanthone (2) and 1,1,2-trimethyl-1,2-dihydro-6H-furo[3,4-b]xanthen-9-one (3). 3-Prenyloxy-4-methylxanthone (4) on Claisen migration in dimethylaniline gave 2-(1,2-dimethylpropenyl)-3-hydroxy-4-methylxanthone (5). Also, Claisen rearrangement of 1 has been studied in (i) DMA+butyric anhydride, (ii) butyric anhydride, (iii) sodium acetate+acetic anhydride, (iv) decalin and (v) vacuum. The structures of 2, 3 and 5 have been assigned on the bases of their ir, pmr and mass spectra.

CLAISEN rearrangement of different prenyloxyxanthones¹⁻⁶ reveals that no observation on the formation of 1,2-dimethylpropenyl side chain in Claisen rearrangement of prenyloxyxanthone. We report here the abnormal Claisen rearrangement of 3-prenyloxy- and 3-prenyloxy-4-methylxanthone.

3-Prenyloxyxanthone (1) on refluxing with dimethylaniline gave two products. The first product was identified as 4-(1,2-dimethylpropenyl)-3-hydroxyxanthone (2) on the basis of its pmr spectra, which showed characteristic quartet at δ 4.38 of one

proton CHCH_3 and two singlets at δ 5.28 and 5.32 for $=\text{CH}_2$ group. In the saturated methyl region there is one methyl singlet at δ 1.66 and one methyl doublet at δ 1.55. In down-field aromatic region was observed one doublet of J 9 Hz at δ 8.16 assigned to proton H-1 indicating that migrated group is at 4-position.

The second product (insoluble in alkali) is the cyclised product 1,1,2-trimethyl-1,2-dihydro-6H-furo[3,4-b]xanthen-9-one (3). Its pmr spectra show characteristic quartet at δ 4.56 of one hydrogen flanked by methyl group and an oxygen atom, and in the up-field region there are two methyl singlets groups at δ 1.6 and 1.3 and one doublet at δ 1.40. There are two doublets of J 9 Hz, the one in up-field aromatic region at 6.78 for H-4 and the other in down-field aromatic region at δ 8.16 for H-5, indicating that it is angular furanoxanthone.

Claisen migration of 1, in dimethylaniline and butyric anhydride mixture, gave 2, 3 and 3-hydroxyxanthone; in butyric anhydride, gave 2 and 3-hydroxyxanthone. While 1, on refluxing with $\text{NaOAc} + \text{Ac}_2\text{O}$ for 70 h failed to give migrated product but gave 3-acetoxyxanthone and the starting material 1; in dcalin (2 h), no migration was observed, but when 1 was refluxed in dcalin for 6 h or heated under vacuum gave 3-hydroxyxanthone.

3-Prenyloxy-4-methylxanthone (4), when refluxed with dimethylaniline gave only one product 2-(1,2-dimethylpropenyl)-3-hydroxy-4-methylxanthone (5). As the pmr spectra of 5 showed quartet of the single proton at δ 3.65 for CHCH_3 , CH_3 doublet at δ 1.55 and two $=\text{CH}_2$ singlet at δ 5.15 and 5.25.

5 on cyclisation with concentrated H_2SO_4 gave 2,2,3,11-tetramethyl-2,3-dihydro-5H-furo[2,3-b]xanthen-9-one (6). Its pmr spectra showed quartet at δ 3.3 for one proton CHCH_3 , CH_3 doublet at δ 1.4 and two singlets at δ 2.35 and 1.38 for aromatic CH_3 and CH_3 in furan ring, respectively, and in

down-field aromatic region only one singlet is observed at δ 7.85 for H-4.

Experimental

The m.ps. are uncorrected. Pmr spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer R-34 (220 MHz) and R-32 (90 MHz) spectrometers using TMS as an internal standard, ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 125 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on an AEMS-12 instrument.

3-Prenyloxyxanthone (1): A mixture of 3-hydroxyxanthone (5 g), prenyl bromide (5 ml), KI (4.0 g) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (25 g) was refluxed in dry acetone (15 ml) on a water-bath for 15 h. The reaction mixture was poured into water and the resulting solid filtered off, washed with dilute NaOH to give a solid (6.9 g). The solid was crystallised from petroleum ether to give **1** as white needles, m.p. 115° (Found: C, 77.5; H, 5.7. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8$ requires: C, 77.1; H, 5.7%).

Claisen migration of 3-prenyloxyxanthone (1): **1** (2 g) was refluxed with dimethylaniline (10 ml) for 4 h. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into cold dilute HCl and extracted with ether. The ether layer was extracted with NaOH solution and the extract on acidification with hydrochloric acid gave a solid which was crystallised from ethyl acetate to give **2** as a white needles, m.p. 194° (Found: C, 76.7; H, 5.3. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8$ requires: C, 77.1; H, 5.7%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300–3 000 (OH) and 1 630 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 8.23 (1H, dd, J 9.2 Hz, H-8), 8.16 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-1), 7.7 (1H, td, J 8, 8.2 Hz, H-6), 7.48 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-5), 7.36 (1H, td, J 8, 8.2 Hz, H-7), 7.0 (1H, s, ArOH), 6.85 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-2), 5.28 and 5.32 (2H, 2xs, =CH₂) and 4.38 (1H, q, CHCH₃), 1.66 (3H, s, CH₃) and 1.55 (3H, d, J 9 Hz, CH₃); m/z 280 (M^+) (53%), 265 ($M^+ - CH_3$) (100%), 250 ($M^+ - 2CH_3$) (21%), 226 ($M^+ - C_4H_8$) (18%) and 212 ($M^+ - C_5H_8$) (74%). Ether solution on evaporation gave a solid and crystallised from ethyl acetate as white needles (**3**), m.p. 185°–60° (Found: C, 77.0; H, 5.8. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8$ requires: C, 77.1; H, 5.7%); ν_{max} 1 655 (C=O) and 1 105 cm^{-1} (dihydrofuran); δ (CDCl₃) 8.3 (1H, dd, J 9.2 Hz, H-7), 8.16 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-5), 7.63 (1H, td, J 9, 9.2 Hz, H-9), 7.41 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-10), 7.3 (1H, td, J 9, 9.2 Hz, H-8), 6.78 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-4), 4.56 (1H, q, J 8 Hz, CHCH₃), 1.6 (3H, s, C₁-CH₃), 1.4 (3H, d, J 8 Hz, CHCH₃) and 1.3 (3H, s, C₁-CH₃); m/z 280 (M^+) (26%), 265 ($M^+ - CH_3$) (100%), 250 ($M^+ - 2CH_3$) (9%).

3-Prenyloxy-4-methylxanthone (4): A mixture of 3-hydroxy-4-methylxanthone (1 g), prenyl chloride (1 ml), anhydrous K_2CO_3 (4 g), KI (0.5 g) was refluxed in dry acetone (150 ml) for 12 h. The reaction mixture was worked up as before, and the resulting solid was crystallised from benzene petroleum ether to give **4**, m.p. 126° (Found: C, 77.1; H, 6.5. $C_{19}H_{18}O_8$ requires: C, 77.5; H, 6.1%).

Claisen migration of 3-prenyloxy-4-methylxanthone (4): **4** (0.4 g) was refluxed in dimethylaniline (5 ml) for 2 h. The reaction mixture on usual work up gave alkali soluble product (100 mg) which was crystallised from alcohol to give **5** as pale yellow needles, m.p. 174° (Found: C, 77.3; H, 6.3. $C_{19}H_{18}O_8$ requires: C, 77.5; H, 6.1%); δ (CDCl₃) 8.28 (1H, dd, J 9.2 Hz, H-8), 8.08 (1H, s, H-1), 7.8–7.38 (3H, m, ArH), 5.25 and 5.15 (2H, 2xs, =CH₂), 3.65 (1H, q, J 8 Hz, CHCH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 1.7 (3H, s, CH₃) and 1.55 (3H, d, J 8 Hz, CHCH₃). The alkali insoluble portion gave **4**.

2,2,3,11-Tetramethyl-2,3-dihydro-5H-furo[2,3-b]xanthen-9-one (6): **5** (50 mg) was titrated with concentrated H_2SO_4 for 15 min on a water-bath. The reaction mixture was then poured on crushed ice, and the resulting solid was filtered off, washed with dilute NaOH and crystallised from CHCl₃ to give **6** as a white needles, m.p. 132° (Found: C, 77.3; H, 6.1. $C_{10}H_{18}O_8$ requires: C, 77.5; H, 6.1%); δ (CDCl₃) 8.25 (1H, dd, J 9 and 1.5 Hz, H-6), 7.85 (1H, s, H-4), 7.7–7.3 (3H, m, H-7, H-8 and H-9), 3.3 (1H, q, J 8 Hz, CHCH₃), 2.56 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 1.6 (3H, s, C₂-CH₃), 1.4 (3H, d, J 8 Hz, CH-CH₃) and 1.38 (3H, s, C₂-CH₃).

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